

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT IN THE READING COMPETENCE AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THIRD GRADERS: BASIS FOR A REMEDIATION PROGRAM

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Parental Involvement in the Reading Competence and Academic Performance of Third Graders: Basis for a Remediation Program

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Abstract

Parents are big part of the success of the learners especially so when we talk about reading competence. Its involvement would require time and effort as in controlling, motivating, monitoring, and providing. This study aims to determine the extent of parental involvement in the reading competence of the third graders at Sta.Cruz, Bagong Nayon 1 and Peace Village Elementary School in Antipolo City. Interviews, literature reviews as well as survey questionnaires were utilized to gather pertinent data. Weighted mean and t-test were used to treat the gathered data. Results revealed that the extent of parental involvement in controlling, motivating, monitoring, and providing are found to be less involved in the reading competence. There is a significant difference between the extent of parental involvement in the reading competence of the Grade 3 learners. However, there is no significant relationship between the extent of parental involvement in the reading competence of Grade 3 pupils and their academic performance in English. This study concludes that the parental involvement in reading competence whether very highly involved or less involved has no effect on the academic performance of the grade 3 learners.

Keywords: *parental involvement, reading competence, academic performance, remediation program*

Introduction

Erik Erikson's (1963) contribution in Developmental Psychology is called Phases about Improvement, where he managed an individual identity flourish contemporary a prearranged rule over eight stages attributed to psychosocial progress. All along a single step, sudden personal struggle a psychosocial dilemma that can either result in positive or negative personality development. In the 5th and 12th years of a child, the psychology crisis that needs resolving is Industry vs. Inferiority. Industry indicates through the child's entanglement mod situations point great as well as tolerant task endure challenged from authority. Inferiority, on the other hand, rises during this crisis is not solved in the right way. Deficiency is a feeling of being a failure and inadequate to do work. In short, if the child, aged 5 to 12 years old, was able to practice ethical and interactive working habits, he is more likely to grow up having the personality of being industrious. On the other hand, if he was not able to practice good working habits, he may grow up always feeling inadequate, with low self-esteem, to do his work. On a more straightforward note, children at this stage are where they need to learn how to read and write, do basic math, and execute their work on their own.

Reading is a fundamental ability that must be enhanced among children during the early years in school. Once this skill is acquired, children's difficulty in comprehending the reading text is likely to be avoided. However, many school children of today have poor comprehension skills when they read. They struggle, and there is much difficulty in understanding the essential thoughts in a given text. This situation may lead learners to feel inadequate and miserable that their interest in reading will fade.

In the children's generation, reading is not as essential and famous as it used to be in the past. Newspapers, magazines, journals, comics, and books have now innovated into a single gadget where one can access all at once. Frequently, these reading materials do not include so many words but rather pictures and amusing visuals, and some even include "podcasts" where the whole text can already narrate to the individual. These so-called "innovation" and "convenience" - are helpful in many ways-lessen the opportunity for the child to learn to read and comprehend.

If this situation continues to used unnecessarily and in too much, they could develop and manifest negative behavior to hide their reading difficulties. As a result, they will only read shorter texts or, worse. They do not read at all.

According to Martin et al. (2015), this scenario contributed to the lack of word attack skills. Thus, learners have limited vocabulary, which severely affects their reading comprehension. It should be in the early childhood education of the learners when the importance of reading could realize. It is at this level when beginning reading instruction takes place.

In the Philippine public schools, it is adhered that some kids step into Grade One through reading fluency while others can barely recognize a single word. Other children have the reading fluency, but cannot listen to all. A more significant number of children show no interest in letters.

Today, there are initiatives that can hopefully turn reading competence more appropriate and relevant to the needs of children. Having a good assessment measures are one of the ways that can yield reliable and concrete improvements in the way these children read. Another way is to provide a reading environment that offers a high level of reading performance, which is equivalent to positive outcomes and serves as an alternative strategy to assure quality and efficiency in the learners' reading readiness.

Current situations in our public schools, however, provide constraints that may lead to low reading literacy like large class sizes,

scarcity of equipment, poor ventilation, and the like.

To turn these reading constraints into success, a collaborative effort of parents and community organizations can persuade the schools and government officials concerned to play an active role and be accountable for their children's learning.

Indeed, learnedness to read emplaces the foundation for future learning and understanding across all areas in the curriculum. Without this foundation, learners will have a hard time in their academic activities not only in reading but also in other areas such as math, Science and Social Studies.

Teachers of first graders have to face a difficult task of recognizing the degree of readiness to read which their young learners have attained by the time classes start in June. Reading willingness might translate as "the time at which a child is capable of learning to read".

A head memorable day of people-financed institutions, fathers, and mothers abide active first education schoolteacher concerning their offspring. That prevails, about the procedure, assuming the father and mother keep learning themselves. Already schools develop into an entrenched, mother, and father mostly surrendered striking obligation since tutoring their offspring through reading directed toward the schools. Regardless of a sudden experience, a certain modernized better mother and father learn by means concerning the interpretation, frequently, and then yield a veritable lethargic aspect contemporarily the learning progress of their offspring.

Some personality theorists believe that intelligence can be enhanced and predetermined through years of practice. This experience means that in the early ages of a child, he must be taught and developed by the first caregivers, the parents. Although children taught how to read, write, and count in pre-school, parents should also involve themselves in teaching their children the basics.

According to Jung, E. (2016), children's new household study continuities hold important attributes toward children's alteration as well as attainment mod striking lifespan appertaining to the institution. That establishes sudden communication aids parental assumption around institution preparedness, household commitment in the family training exercise, with children's attitude toward schools announced through the mother and father, including learning accomplishment in school.

Children or pupils indeed spend most of their day in school with their "second parents." But it is as essential as teachers that parents also affect themselves in the learning capacity of their children. Learning does not stop after individuals have gone to school—knowledge contained in the four walls of the classroom. Education is everywhere, and children need guidance from their role models on how to discover and explore them.

The research designed directed toward investigating on sudden impact regarding parent entanglement mod affecting reading competence related to Third Graders of Sta. Cruz, Bagong Nayon 1, and Peace Village Elementary School in Antipolo City as the basis for a remediation program.

Research Questions

The study determined the parental involvement in the reading competence and academic performance of third-graders; the results of the survey may use as the keystone for the remediation program. Precisely, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of parental involvement in the reading competence of the Third Graders to parent- respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Controlling;
 - 1.2. Motivating;
 - 1.3. Monitoring; and
 - 1.4. Providing?
2. Is there a significant difference between parental involvement in the reading competence of the Grade 3 learners as assessed by teachers and parents respondents?
3. What is the academic performance of the grade 3 learners during their first grading period?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of parental involvement in the reading competence of Grade 3 pupils and their academic performance in English?
5. What may the remediation program be crafted based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This research used the evocative technique of analysis as it purposed at to ascertain the parental participation as well as academic accomplishment in the reading competence of third graders in selected elementary Schools at Antipolo City.

The descriptive methods of research are exploiting surveys as well as interviews used in this study. The illustrative process of this study contracts through collecting pieces of evidence using plotting existing conditions of the situation, and existing access, which takes an affiliation which affects the connection among alterable, challenging of hypothesis, as well as the progress of generalization, values, or concepts that need general cogency.

Hence, the descriptive method used in identifying the current practice of the parents of the third graders of selected Elementary School and their children's readiness in reading will set the direction of this research. The purpose stays to describe the extent of parental participation such as parental control, being a motivator, being a monitor, and being a resource provider to the reading competence of third graders. Frequencies, averages, and percentages were statistical treatments used in examining the data.

This study focused on two variables, such as reading competence and parental involvement, such as parental control, as a motivator, as a monitor, and as a resource provider. The reading competence will be the independent variable, while the parental involvement of the grade three pupils is the dependent variable. The two variables are linked to probe their relationship. This research used an evocative measurable plan. Measurable approaches accentuate existential capacities as well as the mathematical, statistical, or arithmetical exposition of facts composed over interviews, questionnaires, and investigations, or through using pre-prevailing numerical points through figuring methods. The measurable study concentrates on gathering statistical facts then simplify it through sets of individuals or to explain a specific prodigy. This method used because it fits the purpose of determining the relationship of the parental involvement and reading competence of Third Graders.

Participants

The respondents were identified based on the quantity of Grade 3 learners who were categorized to be under the Frustration Level in the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory test.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1 *Respondents of the Study*

School	Teacher		Parent	
	F	Percent	f	Percent
1.Bagong Nayon 1	27	40.91	40	34.19
2.Peace Village	9	13.64	30	25.64
3.Sta. Cruz ES	30	45.45	47	40.17
Total	66	100.00	117	100.00

Based on Table 1, the highest numbers of respondents are from Sta Cruz Elementary School with a frequency of 30 or 45.45% and followed by Bagong Nayon1 Elementary School with 27 or 40.91% and Peace Village ES with 9 or 13.64%frustration-readers.

Instruments

The researcher-made-questionnaire used by the researcher intended precisely on behalf of this research study. The questionnaire consists of two parts; Part 1 covers the profile of the respondents. Section 2 reflects the extent of the reading competence to parental involvement, such as controlling, motivating, monitoring, and providing. This study likewise identified the aspects that the learners needed help.

The research instrument underwent the process of authentication in sequence to assure a hundred percent consistency of outcomes. A cluster of specialists, approximately three members, analyzed and scrutinized the contents of the tool. Their commentaries, as well as recommendations, were measured in the completion of the device. The researcher managed the survey to the respondents.

Procedure

Preceding to the real conduct of the questionnaire, the researcher requested approval overprinted letter to the Schools Division Superintendent, to the Principal of Sta Cruz, Bagong Nayon1, and Peace Village Elementary School. The researcher approached and discussed among grade 3 teachers the nature of this study before gathering of data from parents of learners who were categorized 43 under the Frustration Level during the Phil-IRI test. The recouplement of the survey precisely finished after that the conduct, since the parents assisted by the researcher and other teachers throughout the Homeroom PTA Meeting. The responses of the parents were evaluated and tabulated by the researcher before employing statistical measures.

Data Analysis

For the analysis and interpretation of data, the succeeding statistical conducts employed:

1. Frequency and percentage. Was castoff to acquaint the demographic profile of the third-grader parent's respondents.
2. Weighted Mean. Was employed to determine the level of reading competence of the pupils.
3. T-test. It used to check a degree of difference among parental participation in the reading competence of the Grade 3 learners.
4. Chi-square. It used to test the independence of one variable from another 44 variable. This tool used to ascertain the relationship between the parental involvement of parent respondents on the reading competence of the third graders.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes and interprets the data based on the problems presented.

Problem No. 1. What is the parental involvement in the reading competence of the Third Graders in terms of:

1.1. Controlling

Table 2 presents the mean value and standard deviation on the extent of parental involvement in the reading competence of the third graders in terms of controlling.

As shown in the table on the next page, in terms of parental control, the respondents are moderately involved (MI) in providing a conducive place for child to read with a mean value 2.43. This is followed by reading with the child with a mean value of 3.53. When the least mean value in parental control is taken into consideration, rewards/gives in incentives to the child when he/she succeed in reading process is recorded with the mean value of 1.92. The Teachers are moderately involved (MI) in the reading competence (M=2.6121, SD=.45826); and the Parents were less involved (M=1.8222, SD=.38419). The overall mean obtained a value of 2.22 interpreted as less parental involvement (LI) in controlling 46 their children to achieve reading competence.

Table 2. Mean Value and Standard Deviation on the Extent of Parental Involvement in the Reading Competence of the Third Graders in terms of Controlling

	Teachers			Parents			OVERALL	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	VI	Mean	Std. Deviation	VI	Ave. Mean	VI
1. gives the child enough freedom in choosing the book they like to read (binigyan ang bata ng sapat na kalayaan sa pagpili ng librong nais nilang basahin)	2.2727	.59602	LI	2.0598	.67327	LI	2.17	LI
2. monitors, supervise the reading hour of the child (sinusubaybayan pamantayan ang oras ng pagbabasa ng bata)	2.4848	.63833	LI	1.7607	.71498	LI	2.12	LI
3. practices the child how to read regularly (isinasagawa ang bata kung paano basahin nang regular)	2.6212	.71823	MI	1.7179	.61372	LI	2.17	LI
4. provides conducive place for child to read (nagbibigay ng kasiya-siyang lugar para mabasa ng bata)	3.0303	.65562	MI	2.0000	.43549	LI	2.52	MI
5. consults teacher for progress in reading readiness (kumunsulta sa mga guro para sa kaunlaran sa pagiging handa sa pagbasa)	2.3333	.64051	LI	1.6410	.63601	LI	1.99	LI
6. rewards/gives in incentives to the child when he/she succeed in reading process (gantimpala/binibigay sa mga insentibo sa bata kapag nagtagumpay siya sa proseso ng pagbasa)	2.1515	.70694	LI	1.6838	.58205	LI	1.92	LI
7. provides read with the child visual learning tools (nagbibigay ng basahin sa mga tool sa visual na pag-aaral ng bata)	2.8030	.63778	MI	1.8120	.58622	LI	2.31	LI
8. reads with the child (nagbabasa kasama ang bata)	3.0152	.59465	MI	1.8376	.47265	LI	2.43	LI
9. asks the child to discriminate letters and sounds (hinihiling ng mga bata na makilala ang titik at tunog)	2.7273	.69161	MI	1.8803	.47638	LI	2.30	LI
10. guides the child in playing with letters and sounds (gabayan ang bata sa paglalaro ng mga titik at tunog)	2.6818	.74749	MI	1.8291	.51345	LI	2.26	LI
COMPOSITE MEAN	2.6121	.45826	MI	1.8222	.38419	LI	2.22	LI

Legend: Range of Score 4.50 – 5.00 Very Highly Involved (VHI); 3.50 – 4.49 Highly Involved (HI) 2.50 – 3.49 Moderately Involved (MI); 1.50 – 2.49 Less Involved (LI) 1.00 – 1.49 Not Involved (NI)

When the three lowest mean values in parental control taken into 47 consideration, the respondents were less involved in Monitoring, supervising the reading hour of the child (M=2.19), consults teacher for progress readiness (M=1.99). While rewards/gives incentives to the child when he/she succeed in the reading process (M=1.92). This result implies that parent's lacks involvement in Monitoring and checking the progress of their child in reading and also requires the ability to motivate them by giving rewards and incentives resulted in lesser reading competency.

It is affirmed by (Crosby et al., 2015) in his study that mother and father participation, as well as the total of period consumed in reading at home, were initiated to be the most excellent precise forecasters of follower accomplishment in reading, reading ability progress, and general knowledge.

1.2. Motivating

Table 3 reflects the mean value and standard deviation on parental involvement in the reading competence of the third graders in terms of controlling.

Table 3. Mean Value and Standard Deviation of Parental Involvement in the Reading Competence of the Third Graders in terms of Motivating

	Teachers			Parents			OVERALL	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	VI	Mean	Std. Deviation	VI	Ave. Mean	VI
1. gives the encouragement to explore reading (nagbibigay ng paghihikayat upang galugarin ang pagbabasa)	3.09	0.67	MI	2.1111	0.50	LI	2.60	MI
2. sets a schedule study time and not allowing the use of electronic gadgets if he/she is poor in reading (nagtatakda ng isang naka-iskedyul na oras ng pag-aaral at hindi pinapayagan ang paggamit ng mga elektronikong gadget kung mahirap siya basahin)	2.18	0.49	LI	1.3932	0.56	NI	1.79	LI
3. watches closely the pupil's in reading to readily be of help to him/her when needed (binabantayan ng mabuti ang mag-aaral sa pagbabasa upang madaling maging tulong sa kanya kapag kinakailangan)	2.20	0.44	LI	1.3504	0.55	NI	1.77	LI
4. tries to be a helpful, consistent and firm parent rather than a controlling one (sinusubukan na maging isang kapaki-pakinabang, pare-pareho at matatag na magulang sa halip na isang pagkontrol sa isa)	3.14	0.55	MI	2.0684	0.39	LI	2.60	MI
5. tries to build up pupils self-confidence if i notice that he/she lacks the motivation in studying reading (sinusubukan na palakasin ang tiwala sa sarili ng mga mag-aaral kung napansin kung kulang ang motibasyon sa pag-aaral ng pagbabasa)	3.20	0.44	MI	2.0855	0.38	LI	2.64	MI
6. helps balance the time spent on studies, friends and other activities (nakakatulong na balansehin ang oras na ginugol sa mga pag-aaral, kaibigan at iba pang mga aktibidad)	2.56	0.79	MI	1.641	0.59	LI	2.10	LI
7. gets involved with reading project and activities. (nasasangkot sa pagbabasa ng proyekto at mga aktibidad)	2.77	0.76	MI	1.3675	0.55	NI	2.07	LI
8. encourages son/daughter to express his/her opinion and talk about the difficulties in reading (hinihikayat ang anak na lalaki / anak na babae na ipahayag ang kanyang opinyon at pag-usapan ang mga paghihirap sa pagbabasa)	3.15	0.75	MI	2	0.39	LI	2.58	MI
9. asks the skills he/she has acquired in reading. (tinatanong ang mga kasanayan na nakuha niya sa pagbasa)	2.79	0.73	MI	1.8291	0.50	LI	2.31	LI
10. gives a special treat or reward for obtaining a good grade in reading (nagbibigay ng isang espesyal na paggamot o gantimpala para sa pagkuha ng isang mahusay na grado sa pagbasa)	2.58	0.81	MI	1.8632	0.61	LI	2.22	LI
COMPOSITE MEAN	2.77	0.46	MI	1.7709	0.31	LI	2.27	LI

Legend: Range of Score 4.50 – 5.00 Very Highly Involved (VHI); 3.50 – 4.49 Highly Involved (HI) 2.50 – 3.49 Moderately Involved (MI); 1.50 – 2.49 Less Involved (LI) 1.00 – 1.49 Not Involved (NI)

As gleaned in the Table, parent involvement in terms of parental motivation in the reading competence of the learner obtained an overall mean of 2.27 interpreted as less parental involvement (LI). Teachers are moderately involved (MI) in the reading competence (M=2.77, SD=.46), and the Parents were less involved (M=1.82, SD=.38).

The respondents are moderately involved (MI) in trying to build up pupils' self- 50 confidence if noticed to be lacking in motivation in reading (M=2.64). Trying to be a helpful, consistent, and firm parent rather than a controlling on (M=2.60) encouraging his/her children to express their opinion and talk about the difficulties in reading (M=2.58). The least mean value in parental motivation in learning competence taken into consideration, the respondents rated it Less Involved (LI) in getting involved with reading project and activities (M=2.07); sets a schedule study time and not allowing the use of electronic gadgets if he/she is deficient in reading (M=1.79); watches carefully the pupil's in learning to be of help to him/her when needed readily (M=1.77)

According to Whalley (2017), as children grow, reading motivates them to explore things written in books, thereby acquiring reading lifestyle and learning most possessions, places, happenings, and practice. Parents bring on the foremost influence on accomplishment by providing and helping their education in the homegrown somewhat than assisting activities or events happening at school. This statement hoped for since the study that parents as motivators take part in the reading competence of the learners has not been observed.

It is in contrast with Whalley (2017), with the results of the lowest mean with a verbal interpretation of Not Involved (NI), i.e., closely watch the pupils in reading to be of help to him/her when needed readily. It indicates that the parent's involvement in this particular area should be dealt with accordingly.

1.3. Monitoring

Table 4 presents the mean value and standard deviation of parental participation in the reading competence of the third graders in terms of control.

Being reflected in Table 4, mother and father stay less tangled in monitoring their youngsters' reading competence with the overall mean 2.29 interpreted as less parental involvement (LI). The teachers are moderately involved (MI) in the reading competence (M=2.76, SD=.47), and the Parents were less involved (LI) (M=1.82, SD=.33).

The respondents also mentioned that offers emotional support for the performance, ability, and efforts given to the reading subject (M=2.65); acknowledges successes and attend to difficulties that are related to reading 53 issue (M=2.53); and supports the self-regulation skills, strategies and personal responsibilities for the processes and outcomes in reading (M=2.44).

Table 4. Mean Value and Standard Deviation on Parental Involvement in the Reading Competence of the Third Graders in terms of Monitoring

	Teachers		VI	Parents		VI	OVERALL	
	Mean	Std. Deviation		Mean	Std. Deviation		Ave. Mean	VI
1. consults with the reading teacher for the performance, progress and homework(mga konsultasyon sa guro ng pagbabasa para sa pagganap, pag-unlad at araling-bahay)	2.17	0.57	LI	1.6667	0.57	LI	1.92	LI
2. signs the homework or any complete tasks in reading(pinirmahan ang araling-bahay o anumang kumpletong gawain sa pagbasa)	2.53	0.66	MI	1.812	0.49	LI	2.17	LI
3. structures the time and used in studying reading(istruktura ang oras at ginamit sa pag-aaral sa pagbasa)	2.48	0.66	LI	1.6239	0.57	LI	2.05	LI
4. gives and enforcing expectations, rules and standards for homework(nagbibigay at nagpapatupad ng mga inaasahan, panuntunan at pamantayan para sa araling-bahay)	2.53	0.64	MI	1.6923	0.65	LI	2.11	LI
5. supervises the homework activity(pinangangasiwaan ang aktibidad sa araling-bahay)	2.68	0.66	MI	1.7607	0.50	LI	2.22	LI
6. acknowledges successes and attend to difficulties that are related to reading subject(kinikilala ang mga tagumpay at dumalo sa mga paghihirap na may kaugnayan sa paksa ng pagbasa)	3.03	0.61	MI	2.0256	0.36	LI	2.53	LI

7. reinforces or rewarding efforts given in the homework based on its completion and correctness(nagpapatibay o nagbibigay-kasiyahan sa mga pagsisikap na ibinigay sa takdang aralin batay sa pagkumpleto at kawastuhan nito)	2.48	0.66	LI	1.8205	0.50	LI	2.15	LI
8. offers emotional support for the performance, ability, and efforts given to the reading subject (nag-aalok ng emosyonal na suporta para sa pagganap, kakayahan, at pagsisikap na ibinigay sa paksa ng pagbasa)	3.23	0.70	MI	2.0769	0.48	LI	2.65	LI
9. assists in the completion of the given tasks or homework in reading(tumutulong sa pagkumpleto ng mga naibigay na gawain o araling-bahay sa pagbasa)	2.97	0.74	MI	1.7436	0.54	LI	2.36	LI
10. supports the self-regulation skills, strategies and personal responsibilities for the processes and outcomes in reading(Sinusuportahan ang mga kasanayan sa regulasyon sa sarili, mga diskarte at personal na responsibilidad para sa mga proseso at kinalabasa	2.94	0.74	MI	1.9487	0.37	LI	2.44	LI
COMPOSITE MEAN	2.76	0.47	MI	1.82	0.33	LI	2.29	LI

Legend: Range of Score 4.50 – 5.00 Very Highly Involved (VHI); 3.50 – 4.49 Highly Involved (HI) 2.50 – 3.49 Moderately Involved (MI); 1.50 – 2.49 Less Involved (LI) 1.00 – 1.49 Not Involved (NI)

When it comes to the lowest mean value, respondents reported a less involvement of parents in the area of giving and enforcing expectations, rules and standards for homework ($M=2.11$); structures the time and used in studying reading ($M=2.05$); consults with the reading teacher for the performance, progress, and homework ($M=1.92$). It implies that parents are not taking an ample part in monitoring the reading progression of their children. Consultation with teachers is not that evident. Parents don't prioritize their children's reading and so less visit, and no reading materials are acquired to strengthen the undertaking.

Bartolome et al. (2017) stated that parental involvement, when it comes to the schooling of his/ her youngsters, includes a significant amount of engagement. Individual schools encourage the most substantial parental participation. With mother and father are hands-on in Monitoring to reading, children become more eager. It attests to the study as that parents play a big part as a monitor to the fulfillment of reading competence of their children. If they play to perform, such an undertaking may not be successful.

Table 5 presents the mean value and standard deviation of parental involvement in the reading competence of the third graders in terms of providing.

As depicted in Table 5, in terms of parental provision of resources in reading competence, the overall mean rated 1.84 interpreted as less parental involvement (LI) in providing support to their children to achieve reading competence. The teachers are less involved (LI) in the reading competence ($M=2.02$, $SD=.30$), and the Parents were less concerned ($M=1.66$, $SD=.30$).

The respondents are less involved (LI) in the seven (7) indicators, which range from 1.88 - 2.42. When the least signs assessed, the respondents recorded a non-parental involvement (NI) in paying for voluntary contributions and extra co curricular activities ($M=1.35$); it pays for the reading project and reading activities ($M=1.3$); and pays for the tutor in learning a subject ($M=1.13$). It implies that parents are not willing to extend an extra contribution to their children. It can be due to the financial status of parents where their children enrolled in public school, which suggests that they cannot afford that much. It can also take into account that parents are giving all responsibilities to teachers for their children's education, for which reading is one. Getting a tutor, therefore, is definitely out of their budget.

This study is affirmed by Papelera & Peollio (2013) that active participation 56 of parents in promoting their youngsters' education, providing them security, excellent foundation skills, and positive self-concept plays a big part. If parents fail to perform its role, then the development in the reading of the child is compromised.

Table 5. Mean Value and Standard Deviation on Parental Involvement in the Reading Competence of the Third Graders in terms of Providing

Item	Teachers			Parents			OVERALL	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	VI	Mean	Std. Deviation	VI	Ave. Mean	VI
1. pays for voluntary contributions and extra co-curricular activities(nagbabayad para sa kusang-loob na mga kontribusyon at labis na mga aktibidad na co-curricular)	1.06	0.30	NI	1.64	0.55	LI	1.35	NI
2. pays for the tutor in reading subject(nagbabayad para sa tutor sa paksa ng pagbasa)	1.02	0.12	NI	1.24	0.47	NI	1.13	NI
3. provides transportation for the comfort of the student(nagbibigay ng transportasyon para sa ginhawa ng mag-aaral)	1.29	0.46	NI	2.47	0.79	LI	1.88	LI
4. pays for the reading project and reading activities(nagbabayad para sa pagbabasa ng proyekto at mga aktibidad sa pagbasa)	1.08	0.32	NI	1.53	0.60	LI	1.3	NI
5. provides books/materials needed in reading subject(nagbibigay ng mga libro / materyales na kinakailangan sa pagbabasa ng paksa)	2.61	0.63	MI	1.79	0.57	LI	2.2	LI
6. provides an appropriate place for the pupils to study(nagbibigay ng isang angkop na lugar para sa mga mag-aaral na pag-aralan)	2.82	0.58	MI	2.03	0.53	LI	2.42	LI
7. gives reward for the achievement in reading(nagbibigay ng gantimpala para sa tagumpay sa pagbasa)	2.15	0.50	LI	1.65	0.62	LI	1.9	LI
8. provides educational videos for beginners in reading(nagbibigay ng mga video na pang-dukasyon para sa mga nagsisimula sa pagbasa)	2.50	0.69	MI	1.73	0.48	LI	2.11	LI
9. makes flashcards of syllables to familiarize pupils in reading(gumagawa ng mga flashcards ng syllables upang maging pamilyar sa mga mag-aaral sa pagbasa)	2.90	0.68	MI	1.27	0.48	NI	2.08	LI
10. posts letters of alphabet with pictures to recognize letters easily(mag-post ng mga titik ng alpabeto na may mga larawan upang madaling makilala ang mga titik)	2.83	0.65	MI	1.25	0.47	NI	2.04	LI
COMPOSITE MEAN	2.02	0.30	LI	1.66	0.30	LI	1.84	LI

Legend: Range of Score 4.50 – 5.00 Very Highly Involved (VHI); 3.50 – 4.49 Highly Involved (HI) 2.50 – 3.49 Moderately Involved (MI); 1.50 – 2.49 Less Involved (LI) 1.00 – 1.49 Not Involved (NI)

Problem No. 2 Is there a significant difference between parental involvements in the reading competence of the Grade 3 learners, as assessed by the two groups of respondents?

Table 6 manifests the t-test on the difference in the extent of parental involvement in the reading competence of the Grade 3 learners as assessed by the two groups of respondents.

Table 6. Significant Difference of the Respondents' Assessment in Parental Involvement in the Reading Competence of the Grade 3 Learners

Parental Involvement		Mean	SD	T-value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Controlling	Teacher	2.61	.45826	7.602	<.00001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Student	2.05	.67327	T-value	P-value		
Motivating	Teacher	2.77	.46060	6.377	<.00001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Student	1.78	.30627	T-value	P-value		
Monitoring	Teacher	2.77	.46974	7.802	<.00001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Student	1.82	.33044	T-value	P-value		
Providing	Teacher	2.02	.30131	1.276	.10903	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Student	1.65	.30458	Mean	Std.		

Table 6 shows that Controlling has a t-value 7.602 which is greater than the critical value 1.96 (p -value $0.00001 < 0.05 \alpha$). It shows that there is an important variance among the extent of Parental controlling and reading competence of the learners in Grade 3.

In terms of Parent motivation, a t-value 6.377 is superior to the vital rate 1.96 (p -value $0.00001 < 0.05 \alpha$). The displays mentioned above that there is a substantial modification between the extent of parental motivation and reading competence of the learners in Grade 3.

With regard to Parent monitoring, a t-value 7.802 is greater than the critical value 1.96 (p -value $0.00001 < 0.05 \alpha$). It shows a particularly significant difference among the extent of parental monitoring and reading competence of the Grade 3 58 learners. Parental monitoring affects the reading competence of learners.

In the aspect of Parent providing resources, a t-value 1.276 is higher than the critical value of 1.96 (p -value $0.10903 > 0.05 \alpha$). It shows that there is no significant difference between the extent of parental provision and reading competence of the Grade 3 learners. It means that the scope of providing the resources of the parents does not affect the reading competence of the learners.

Parent controlling, monitoring, and motivating are factors in reading competence while providing does not. This further implies that without parental involvement in the former three aspects, learning competence is compromised. In other words, it might not be successful. On the other hand, whether the parent will provide reading materials or not, the program will still commence.

Problem No. 3 What is the academic performance of the learners in grade 3 during their first grading period?

Table 7 introduces the frequency and percentage of the academic performance of grade 3 learners during their first grading period.

Table 7. Frequency and Percentage of the Academic Performance of Grade 3 Learners during the First Grading Period

Category	Frequency	Percent
74.00	5	4.3
75.00	22	18.8
76.00	61	52.1
77.00	27	23.1
78.00	2	1.7
Total	117	100.0

The Table reveals that most of the learners have a grade of 76 with a frequency of 61 or 52.1%. It is followed by those who got 77 with a rate of 27 or 23.1%. Next is the grade category of 75, with a frequency of 22 or 18.8%. Then grade group of 74 with a rate of 5 or 4.3%. Finally, the least obtained grade is 78, with 2 or 1.7%. It means that most pupils have poor academic performance, as reflected by their class, which ranges from 74-78. Poor performance can be equated to low reading abilities as this serves as the foundation of understanding the lesson.

Problem No. 4 Is there a significant relationship between parental involvements in the reading competence of Grade 3 learners and their academic performance in English?

Table 8 presents the chi-square value of the significant relationship between 60 parental involvement in the reading competence of Grade 3 learners and their academic performance in English.

As shown in Table 8, there is no meaningful relationship among the parental involvement in controlling, motivating, monitoring, and providing in the reading competence of their children's academic performance in English, $\chi^2(20, 61, N=117) = 60.208, 46.433, 48.624, 64.465$ with its corresponding p values of .838, .815, .923, .323, ($p > 0.05$) respectively.

Parent involvement is not connected to the academic presentation of the learners in English (99.2%). It implies that since mother and father are less tangled in the reading competence concerning their youngsters, it reflects that the aspects of parent involvement don't relate to each other. It means that the less participation of the parents justifies the poor academic performance of their youngsters.

Table 8. *Chi-square Value of the Significant Relationship between Parental Involvement in the Reading Competence of Grade 3 Learners and Their Academic Performance in English*

Case Processing Summary						
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Controlling * Academic Performance	117	99.2%	1	0.8%	118	100.0%
Motivating * Academic Performance	117	99.2%	1	0.8%	118	100.0%
Monitoring * Academic Performance	117	99.2%	1	0.8%	118	100.0%
Providing * Academic Performance	117	99.2%	1	0.8%	118	100.0%

Source of Variation	x ² -value	Df	Sig.	Decision	Remarks
Controlling	60.208	20	.838	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Motivating	46.433	20	.815	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Monitoring	48.624	20	.923	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Providing	64.465	20	.323	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, several assumptions are drawn. Firstly, parental involvement in controlling, motivating, monitoring, and providing is found to have a limited impact on the English reading competence of third graders. Secondly, there is a significant difference between the levels of parental participation in the reading competence of Grade 3 learners, as assessed by two groups of respondents. Thirdly, learners should study hard to maintain their passing grades throughout all grading periods, with the assistance of both teachers and parents. Fourthly, there is no significant relationship between the extent of parental involvement in the reading competence of Grade 3 pupils and their academic performance in English. Finally, Project START (Sustainable Techniques and Alternative Reading Task) may be crafted based on the findings of the research.

Based on these findings, several recommendations are proposed. Parents must consistently be involved in their children's reading activities as a follow-up to the learners' progress. They should consider enrolling their children in reading tutorials to help develop their skills. Additionally, parents should set limits on electronic gadget use if their child is deficient in reading and should regularly consult with reading teachers about their child's performance, progress, and homework. Teachers and parents should collaborate closely to support reading development among learners. Learners themselves should strive to maintain their passing grades throughout all grading periods, with the support of both teachers and parents. Even though there is no significant relationship between parental involvement and reading competence, it is recommended that parents and teachers continue to work together in developing the learners' skills. The implementation of Project START is highly recommended, as it is based on the research results and is expected to benefit the learners. Lastly, future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies using other variables.

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